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Effectiveness of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies among Smallholder Farmers in Bade L. G. A. of Yobe State, Nigeria

Ahmadu Musa Dagona¹; Salisu Abdullahi² & Uba Hussaini Dangata³

¹(Chief Lecturer)

Department of Primary Education

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

Phone no: 08067699294, 07086862291

Email: ahmadumusadagona@gmail.com

²Department of Agricultural Education

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

Phone no: 08065033058

³Department of Social Studies

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

Phone no: 08067360445

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to identify and examine climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder farmers in Bade L.G.A. of Yobe state. Mixed method (survey questionnaire and interview) were used to gather data for this study. Sample were drawn from 4 wards in the study area and 200 copies of questionnaire were purposively administered to the smallholder farmers (household heads) and same 200 were retrieved, while 4 Agricultural Extension Officers (AEOs) were interviewed. Moreover, 40 farmers were randomly selected (10 from each ward) for four consecutive Focus Group Discussions (FGD). Data collected were analysed using simple percentages and frequencies, and results show that adaptation strategies being used by the farmers in the study area include crop diversification (84%), early planting (76%), growing drought resistant varieties (59%), soil and water conservation practices (31%), development of irrigation infrastructure (53%), and selling of livestock (21%). Moreover, Chi-Square analysis shows that socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers affect their level of adoption of adaptation strategies. The paper therefore recommends that farmers in the study area be enlightened about the prospects of agro-forestry. Agricultural institutions also need to identify those crops being diversified in the study area in order to provide improved varieties that will withstand drought as well as diseases and pests, and mature quickly. Finally the study suggests that effective policy measures should be taken to promote the adoption of climate change adaptation strategies.

Keywords: Climate Change, Adaptation, Smallholder farmers, Adaptation Strategies.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Climate change refers to a change in the state of the climate that can be identified by changes that persists for an extended period, usually decades or longer (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC),

2007). The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (2007) have argued that climate change may have a permanent negative impact on the natural resource base upon which agriculture thrives especially considering that it is happening at a time of growing demand for basic human requirements such as food, fibre and fuel.

Over the past few decades, climate change has adversely affected both physical and biological systems in most continents across the globe. According to Danso-Abbeam *et al.* (2021), in the past 30 years climate change has contributed to global agricultural production declining by 1–5 percent per decade. Its effects are also predicted to manifest in severe consequences for the global agricultural sector, especially in tropical and sub-tropical regions. Where the economies of a majority of countries are largely driven by the agricultural sector, such as in sub-Saharan Africa, the impacts of climate change are particularly severe. The rapid and uncertain changes in temperature and rainfall pattern in the subcontinent deepen the vulnerability of the agricultural systems, especially food production (IPCC, 2014b). This trend is expected to intensify in the future with the predicted climate change in tropical regions as it is expected to cause a significant decline in the production of important and staple food crops in such regions (Danso-Abbeam *et al.*, 2021).

The threat of global climate change has caused concern among scientists as crop growth could be severely affected by changes in key climatic variables (i.e., rainfall and temperature) and agricultural production and food security could be affected both globally and locally (FAO, 2019). Although the effects of changes in climate on crop yields are likely to vary greatly from region to region, anticipated changes are expected to have large and far-reaching effects predominantly in tropical zones of the developing world with precipitation regimes ranging from semiarid to humid (Zangre *et al.*, 2024). Hazards include increased flooding in low-lying areas, greater frequency and severity of droughts in semiarid areas, and excessive heat conditions, all of which can limit crop growth and yields.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2007) in its fourth Assessment report warns that warming by 2100 will be worse than previously expected, with a probable temperature rise of 1.8 degrees centigrade to 4 degrees centigrade and a possible rise of up to 6.4 degrees centigrade. According to Onyango and Nzungya (2023) as temperatures continue to rise, the impacts on agriculture will be significant. These impacts are already being experienced by many communities in countries of the Southern hemisphere. There will also be an increase in droughts and heavy precipitation events, which will further damage crops through crop failure, flooding, soil and wind erosion. An increase in intense tropical cyclone activities will cause crop damage in coastal ecosystems, while sea level rise will reduce cropping areas and will salinize coastal aquifers. Pacific islands and large deltas are already being affected by these phenomena. Poor farmers in developing countries are especially vulnerable to these impacts of climate change because of their geographic exposure, low incomes, greater reliance on agriculture, as well as limited capacity to seek alternative livelihoods (Onyango and Nzungya, 2023).

There is increasing evidence that climate change will strongly affect the African continent and will be one of the challenging issues for future development, particularly in the drier regions (Alemayehu and Bewket, 2017; Adger *et al.*, 2012). The challenge is composed of the likely impacts of climate change on ecosystem services, agricultural production, and livelihoods as well as the limited resilience and high vulnerability characterizing regions dominated by economic poverty, subsistence food production, and a low and highly variable natural production potential. An economic analysis of 9000 farmers in 11 African countries predicted falling farm revenues with current climate scenarios (Alemayehu and Bewket, 2017).

Using two global circulation models, a study at national level in Mali predicted future economic losses and increased risk of hunger due to climate change (Majid and Kruse, 2017). It seems clear that the combination of high climatic variability, poor infrastructure, economic poverty, and low productivity will constitute important challenges for Africa and the Sahelian countries in particular. Nevertheless, rural communities in the Sahelian zone of West Africa have always managed their resources and livelihoods in the face of challenging environmental and socio-economic conditions (Bosello, 2018). They have to a large extent been able to develop their livelihood strategies in a way which enables them to constantly cope with and adapt to an erratic climate, severe pest attacks, changing policies at local, national, and global levels, and so on. According to Majid and Kruse (2017), the scientific agreement that climate

change is happening and will continue well into the future regardless of the effectiveness of mitigation measures has reiterated the need to understand how farmers and pastoralists in the Sahel have coped with climate variability and change in order to guide the strategies for adaptation in the future. Climate change is expected to adversely affect agricultural production, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa where the agricultural sector forms the backbone of most countries' economies. This thus holds true for the agriculture sector of the northern region of Yobe state which is largely rain-fed and dominated by smallholder farmers with minimal livelihood alternatives.

However, in continuous coping with extreme weather events and climatic variability, farmers living in harsh environments in the regions of Africa, Asia and Latin America have developed and/or inherited complex farming systems that have the potential to bring solutions to many uncertainties facing humanity in an era of climate change. These systems have been managed in ingenious ways, allowing small farming families to meet their subsistence needs in the midst of environmental variability without depending much on modern agricultural technologies (FAO, 2019). Although many of these systems have collapsed or disappeared in many parts of the world, the stubborn persistence of millions of hectares under traditional farming is living proof of a successful indigenous agricultural strategy and constitutes a tribute to the "creativity" of small farmers throughout the developing world (IPCC, 2007). Until today, well into the first decade of the 21st century, there are in the world millions of smallholders, family farmers and indigenous people practising resource-conserving farming which is testament to the remarkable resiliency of agro-ecosystems in the face of continuous environmental and economic change, while contributing substantially to food security at local, regional and national levels (Lamichhane et. al., 2022).

1.1 Climate change

The United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2014a) defined climate change as a rise in the earth's global average temperature and the climate effects caused by this temperature increase. It also refers to significant changes in global temperature, precipitation, wind patterns and other measures of climate that occur over several decades or longer (Onyango and Nzenya, 2023). Climate change means any long-term change in the average weather patterns in a particular area. Average weather patterns include average temperature, rainfall, wind conditions and numerous other climatic conditions. These changes may take place due to the dynamic processes of the Earth (e.g. volcanic eruptions or earthquakes), due to external forces (e.g. changes in the intensity of solar radiation or fall of large meteorites), or due to human activities (e.g. deforestation, tree burning or the three types of pollution – land, air and water), resulting in an ecological imbalance (United Nations Environment, 2017).

1.2 Adaptation

This means adapting to life in a changing climate. IPCC (2001) defined adaptation as adjustments to natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. It encompasses adjusting to actual or expected future climate (IPCC, 2014b; Environmental Protection Agency, 2016). The aim is to reduce our susceptibility to the harmful effects of climate change (like drought, sea-level rise or more intense extreme weather events). Adaptation is the process by which stakeholders (including farmers) mitigate the adverse impacts of climate on their livelihoods and involves adjustments in lifestyle and economic structure in order to reduce the vulnerability of a system to climate change and variability (Lamichhane et. al., 2022). Adaptation, according to Campos, Velázquez and McCall (2014), can be defined as the "adjustment of socio-ecological systems in response to actual, perceived, or expected environmental changes and their impacts". Adaptation is a key concept in climate change research; because responsiveness and adaptation mechanisms act as indicators of whether social systems are becoming more resilient to climate change impacts. In social systems, the term adaptation refers to adjustments in the behavior and characteristics of a human group that enhance its ability to cope with external stresses; consequently the direct effect of adaptation is to reduce individual and social vulnerability. It also includes making the most of any potential beneficial opportunities associated with climate change (for example, longer growing seasons or increased yields in some regions). Adaptation can be viewed as reducing the severity of many impacts when adverse conditions prevail. That is, adaptation reduces the level of damages that might have otherwise occurred (Campos, Velázquez and McCall, 2014).

Throughout history, people and societies have adjusted to and coped with changes in climate and extremes with varying degrees of success. Climate change (drought in particular) has been at least partly responsible for the rise and fall of civilizations. As we know it, earth's climate has been relatively stable for the past 12,000 years and this stability has been crucial for the development of our modern civilization and life. Modern life is tailored to the stable climate we have become accustomed to. As our climate changes, we will have to learn to adapt. The faster the climate changes, the harder it could be (Global Agriculture, 2019).

1.3 Smallholder farmer

According to Mgbenka, Mbah and Ezeano (2015) more than 80 percent of farmers in Nigeria are small holder farmers. Agriculture is a major contributor to Nigeria's gross domestic product (GDP) and small-scale farmers play a dominant role in this contribution. By international standard, a farm that is less than 10 hectares is classified as small scale (Mgbenka, Mbah and Ezeano, 2015). By this definition therefore, any farmer cultivating a land that is less than 10 hectares is referred to as a smallholder farmer. A small scale farmer depends on their efficiency in the utilization of basic production resources available to them. The Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) (2019) defined smallholder farmer as "an agricultural holding run by a family using mostly (or only) their own labour and deriving from that work a large but variable share of its income, in kind or in cash". The family relies on its agricultural activities for at least part of the food consumed – be it through self-provision, non-monetary exchanges or market exchanges. The family members also engage in activities other than farming, locally or through migration. The holding relies on family labour with limited reliance on temporary hired labour, but may be engaged in labour exchanges within the neighbourhood or a wider kinship framework.

South Africa Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (2012) defined smallholder farmers as farmers that possess the following characteristics:

- They usually own small-based plots of land.
- Normally grow subsistent crops with one or two cash crops.
- Permanently rely on family labour.

1.4 Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

Adaptation strategies assist smallholder farmers to achieve their food, income and livelihood security and it allows them to maintain livelihoods in the face of climate change. Therefore, farmers can reduce the potential damage by making tactical responses to climate change (Tabbo and Amadou, 2017). Bryan *et al.* (2013) examined farmers' perceptions of climate change, ongoing adaptation measures, and factors influencing farmers' decisions to adapt in Kenya. The results showed that while many households have made small adjustments to their farming practices in response to climate change (in particular, changing planting decisions), few households are able to make more costly investments, for example in agroforestry or irrigation, although there is a desire to invest in such measures. Alemayehu and Bewket (2017) found that the most widely used coping strategy in Ethiopia was selling livestock (85% of the respondents), followed by changing consumption pattern (76% of the respondents). Changing crop planting dates was the most preferred adaptation option (89% of the respondents), while irrigation as an adaptation strategy was used only by 10% of the surveyed farmers. Likewise, Elum, Modise and Marr (2017) also found planting drought-tolerant varieties as a common adaptation strategy among the farmers of Gauteng, Limpopo and Mpumalanga in South Africa.

In 2018, Fadina and Barjolle conducted a survey in Benin Republic which reveals that farmers adopt many strategies in response to climate change. These strategies include "Crop–livestock diversification and other good practices (mulching, organic fertilizer)," "Use of improved varieties, chemical fertilizers and pesticides," "Agroforestry and perennial plantation" and "Diversification of income-generating activities." The findings also revealed that most of the respondents use these strategies in combination. Recently, smallholder farmers in three different locations in Senegal's semi-arid zone have utilized various Climate-Smart-Technologies (CST) to mitigate the effects of climate change. These technologies include the use of improved crop varieties, crop rotation with leguminous plants, adjusting planting dates, practicing Farmer Managed Natural Regeneration (FMNR), and diversifying crops (Zangre *et al.*, 2024).

1.5 Problem Statement/Justification

Climate change is perhaps the most serious environmental threat to the fight against hunger, malnutrition, disease and poverty in Africa, essentially because of its impact on agricultural productivity (Global Climate Change, 2018). Climate change and land degradation result in decreasing yields and crop failures in Nigeria (including Bade LGA of Yobe state) and have caused further impoverishment of Nigeria's poorest region. Farmers in Bade LGA of Yobe state have diversified their livelihoods to adapt to uncertain environmental conditions in various ways. While traditionally a diversification of the production and migration were the prime means of adaptation, many farmers have started to intensify their production by adopting shallow groundwater irrigation for vegetable gardening for Nigeria's urban markets. This has helped to cope with a changing environment, ameliorated poverty and reversed rural-urban migration, while the local hydrology curbed an over-exploitation of groundwater resources, commonly associated with an uncontrolled farmer-driven expansion of groundwater irrigation.

Because agricultural production remains the main source of income for most rural communities in Bade LGA, adaptation of the agricultural sector to the adverse effects of climate change will be imperative to protect the livelihoods of the poor and to ensure food security. Adaptation can greatly reduce vulnerability to climate change by making smallholder farmers of Bade LGA better able to adjust to climate change and variability, moderating potential damages, and helping them cope with adverse consequences.

In response to expected changes, governments supported by international cooperation have intensified their efforts to empower the agricultural sector to effectively adapt to climate change at both national and local levels. This holds particularly true for the Northern region of Yobe, one of the driest savannah regions of Nigeria, where an increasing number of droughts and bushfires heavily affect nature and humans. It is found to be one of the most vulnerable and exposed regions to climate change and variability in Nigeria. At the receiving end of these impacts are millions of poor smallholder farmers with minimal livelihood alternatives who are already marginalised, poor and largely rely on nature for food and income. Their rain-fed agriculture, forming the dominant economic activity in the region relies heavily on a single and already modified rainy season (Antwi-Agyei, Dougill and Stringer, 2015). Smallholder farmers are one of the most vulnerable groups to climate change, yet efforts to support farmer adaptation are hindered by the lack of knowledge of climate change adaptation strategies, absence of information about the factors that determine the choice of adaptation strategies as well as dearth of knowledge of barriers to climate change adaptation strategies (Majeed and Kruse, 2017). Thus, more information is needed on how different types of smallholder farmers vary in their perceptions and responses to climate change, factors that determine the choice of adaptation strategies, barriers to climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder farmers and how to tailor adaptation programs to different smallholder farmer contexts. This research was therefore motivated by the need to fill in the above gap in knowledge by providing empirically tested data on the effectiveness of climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder farmers in Bade local government area on which the study area's future climate change adaptation policies could be based.

Several studies have been undertaken to identify climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder farmers in Nigeria (Medugu *et al.*, 2011; Bosello, 2018; Danso-Abbeam *et al.*, 2021). However, most of these studies failed to assess the effectiveness of climate change adaptation strategies. This presents an important limitation, since farmers' responses to climate change or their choice of adaptation strategies is being dictated by a host of environmental and socio-economic factors. This provides a basis, as well as point of departure from other studies, as the knowledge of the effectiveness of adaptation strategies has potential to assist policy to strengthen adaptation at the local level.

Furthermore, to the best of my knowledge, there is no study conducted previously to investigate the effectiveness of climate change adaptation strategies in Bade L.G.A. of Yobe state, Nigeria. Thus, an understanding of why and how households choose adaptation options in this difficult environment is crucial and can guide policymakers on ways to promote adaptation, by identifying target variables that enhance the use of effective adaptation measures.

1.6 Aim and Objectives

The main aim of this study is to identify climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder farmers in Bade L.G.A. of Yobe state. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

- a) To identify the climate change adaptation strategies being used by the farmers in the study area;
- b) To assess the effectiveness of climate change adaptation strategies being used by smallholder farmers in the study area.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study provides evidence based data to authorities responsible for planning climate change adaptation policies such as Yobe State Ministry of Agriculture. It also provides Non-Governmental Organisations and Development Partners with vital information that can complement their efforts in environmental conservation. More so, this research may help future researchers conducting research on climate change and similar topics to investigate other adaptation strategies being adopted in the study area. The research also increases public (local farmers) awareness of the effects of climate change there by making them have a greater appreciation of adaptation strategies.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

2.1.1 Geographical Location

Bade Local Government Area (LGA) is situated in the semi-arid region of northern Nigeria. It is located in Yobe State at about 186km away from the state capital Damaturu. It lies approximately between latitude 12°30'N to 12°52'N and longitude 10°35'E to 11°13'E (figure 2.1). It shares border with Bursali L.G.A. to the East, Nguru and Karasuwa L.G.As to the North, Hadejia L.G.A. of Jigawa State to the southwest, and Jakusko L.G.A. to the southeast. Bade Local Government covers an area of about 1,122 square kilometers with a population of 198, 400 according to 2016 population projection.

2.1.2 Climate

The climate of Bade is hot and dry for most part of the year, but the hottest months are March and April. It has a recorded temperature range of 38°C and 40°C, which falls during rain fall and harmattan seasons to between 18°C and 28°C (Suleiman, 2007). The rainy season usually starts from June or July and ends in September or October, with rainfall reading of 500-1000mm per annum.

2.1.3 Vegetation

The climate described above affects the vegetation of the area resulting into few trees, shrubs and grasses. Despite these however, the area has a fairly good number of trees and provides excellent grazing pasture for animals. As such, the area attracts a lot of Fulani herdsmen from many parts of Nigeria. The common trees found in the area includes; *Acacia seyel*, *Balanite aegyptiaca*, *Azadiracta indica*, *Adansonia digitata*, *Faidherbia albida*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Hyphaene thebaica* and *Anogeissus leiocarpus*.

2.1.4 Hydrology

The topographical relief of Bade L.G.A. can generally be described as flat. The most important geographical feature of Bade L.G. is its famous river (River Yobe), from which the state derived its name. The greater part of the local government is covered by a number of rivers which usually flood the area and empty into the main River Yobe which itself empties into the Lake Chad (Suleiman, 2007).

Figure 2.1: Map of Yobe state showing the study area.

Source: Pantami, 2020.

2.1.5 Economic Activities

The main occupation of bade people is farming, about 70% of the population are farmers (Wakawa *et al.*, 2017). Most farmers are involved in rain-fed and irrigated agriculture, together with livestock rearing. Rain-fed farming is practiced mainly in the upland farms, characterized mainly by production of staple food crops such as sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*), pearl millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*), maize (*Zea mays*), sesame (*Sesamum indicum*), cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) (Wakawa *et al.*, 2017). Traditionally, dry season irrigated farming, locally known as fadama is practiced along the river Yobe floodplain. In recent years with the introduction of pump-set irrigation system, irrigated farming has expanded to higher ground and is no longer restricted to the floodplain. In this area, irrigated wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and vegetables are grown. Vegetables grown under irrigation are profitable cash crops which include; onions (*Allium cepa*), sweet and chilli peppers (*Capsicum annum*), tomato (*Lycopersicon esculenta*), okra (*Hibiscus esculentus*), aubergine (*Solanum melongena*), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*), “garden egg” and “egusi” melon (*Citrullus lanatus*). Various types of agricultural land tenure systems exist in the study area, among which include inheritance, renting, purchasing, borrowing and share cropping. Majority of households own farmland under the inheritance system whereby land belongs to the family and is passed on from one generation to another by the household head (Wakawa *et al.*, 2017).

Livestock rearing is the next occupation of the people. The livestock are mostly in the rural areas. Animals reared include cattle, sheep, goats, donkeys, horses, and few camels. Fishing is another occupation of bade people because of rivers and tributaries that surround their villages. Presently, there are some traders and civil servants also among Bade people.

2.2 Types and Sources of Data

Both quantitative (survey questionnaire) and qualitative (Focus Group Discussion) methods were used to gather information in this study. The questionnaire was administered to the smallholder farmers (household heads) in the study area, where as the Focus Group was interviewed.

2.3 Reconnaissance Survey

A reconnaissance survey was carried out in the study area to identify the farming and related activities of farmers. This helped the researcher to gather preliminary data and got a broad and quick examination of the study area. It also assisted the researcher to identify key features, patterns and potential areas of interest.

2.4 Sampling of Study Locations

There are ten wards in the study area namely:

1. Dagona ward
2. Gwiyo Kura ward
3. Katuzu ward
4. Lawan Musa ward
5. Lawan Fannami ward
6. Sabongari ward
7. Sarkin Hausawa ward
8. Sugum-Tagali ward
9. Usur-Dawayo ward
10. Zango ward

Out of these, four wards were purposively sampled because they are located in villages where there is enough land for farming and almost each and every household engages in one farming activity or the other. The remaining six wards are located within the local government headquarter (Gashua) which is congested, no land for farming and majority of its residents do not engage in any farming activity (Figure 2.2). Fifty households were randomly selected from each of the four wards whose people engage fully in farming. The four wards purposively selected include:

1. Dagona ward
2. Gwiyo Kura ward
3. Sugum-Tagali ward and
4. Usur-Dawayo ward

2.5 Population and Sampling Procedure

2.5.1 Characteristics of the Population

The population for this research were smallholder farmers (household heads) in Bade LGA above the age of thirty five years and Agricultural Extension Officers (AEOs). Older smallholder farmers were targeted at because they are the ones that have stayed long enough to notice any changes in the environment.

Figure 2.2: Map of Bade LGA showing the study area and selected wards.

Source: Pantami, 2024.

2.5.2 Sampling Frame

The sampling frame comprise of all smallholder farmers and Agricultural Extension Officers in the ten wards of Bade LGA.

2.5.3 Sample Size Determination

From the 2006 National Population Census data projection, Dagona ward has 500 households, Gwiyo kura has 550 households, Sugum Tagali has 450 households and Usur Dawayo has 500 households. Thus, ten percent of the households in each of the four wards will be randomly selected by adopting the 10% sampling size formula recommended by Pamela Alreck and Robert Settle (2004) and Ronan Conroy (2016). Consequently, 50, 55, 45 and 50 respondents will be randomly selected from Dagona, Gwiyo kura, Sugum Tagali and Usur Dawayo wards respectively. Therefore a total of two hundred (200) respondents will be sampled from all the four wards.

2.6 Data Collection Procedure

2.6.1 Questionnaire

A questionnaire (Appendix A) was administered to smallholder farmers (household heads) in the study area, while Agricultural Extension Officers were interviewed. Fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were directly administered to each of the four settlements purposively selected.

2.6.2 Interview

Normally there is one Agricultural Extension Officer in each ward, so a total of four AEOs were interviewed. The results of the interview were jotted down there and then. Questions asked during the interview can be seen in Appendix B.

2.6.3 Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

Ten smallholder farmers were randomly selected from each ward with the help of their community leaders for four consecutive Focus Group Discussions. This means that a total of forty farmers were interviewed. The result of the FGD was jotted down there and then. Questions asked during the interview can be seen in Focus Group Discussion Guide (Appendix B).

2.7 Data Analysis

Data obtained both from interview and questionnaire was summarised in tables under different titles/headings such as: general information from the respondents; and climate change adaptation strategies. Descriptive statistical tools (average and percentage) were employed to analyse the data under each table and the results presented into charts and graphs. This helped in answering the research questions of the study. Moreover, inferential statistics, precisely chi-square was employed to find out the relationship between age of farmers, number of children, educational level of farmers and their level of adoption of climate change adaptation strategies.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, an attempt was made to present in detail the data collected in the course of this research with the aim of achieving the stated objectives of this study. This chapter further discussed and summed up primary findings of the research with the aim of arriving at conclusions that will underpin road map and recommendations prescribed.

3.1 Socio-demographic Characteristics

3.1.1 Age of Smallholder Farmers

Age distribution of smallholder farmers in Bade Local Government Area is presented in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
40-49	82	41
50-59	73	36.5
60-69	39	19.5
70-75	6	3
Total	200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

As can be seen in the table 4.1, majority of the farmers sampled belong to the age bracket of 40-49 with 82%, followed by age bracket 50-59 with 37%. Age bracket 70-75 recorded the lowest percentage (3%) and is the weakest group, while age group 40-49 represents the most active age bracket in the study area. Age of household head, which represents experience, affects adaptation to climate change positively because experience in farming increases the probability of uptake of adaptation measures to climate change. Farming experience also facilitates the identification and implementation of any adaptation strategy (Lamichhane et. al., 2022; Deressa et al., 2009; Gbetibouo, 2009).

3.1.2 Gender of Smallholder Farmers

Gender distribution of smallholder farmers is presented in table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	191	95.5
Female	09	4.5
Total	200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

Table 4.2 shows that 95% of the farmers sampled in the study area are male while only 5% are female. The higher percentage for male respondents may be due to the religious and cultural beliefs of the people in the study area which automatically make men (father) the head of every household. Even in situations where the father is dead, the eldest son takes over as the household head. Gender is very significant in climate change adaptation studies since many researches have shown that sex is an important variable

affecting adaptation decision at the farm level. For example, Deressa *et al.* (2009) and Nhemachena and Hassan (2009) found that, male-headed households adapt more readily to climate change.

3.1.3 Level of Education of Smallholder Farmers

Educational attainments of the farmers were presented in table 3.3 below.

Table 3.3 Level of Education of Farmers

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Primary Certificate	28	14
SSCE	68	34
Diploma/NCE	85	42.5
HND/Degree	16	8
Master	3	1.5
Total	200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

Results show that 14% of the farmers sampled just attended primary school, 34% have SSCE certificates, and 43% possess Diploma/NCE certificates, while only 1% has master degree. The educational attainment of farmers is also relevant in researches of this kind because educated and experienced farmers are expected to have more knowledge and information about climate change and agronomic practices they can use in response. Moreover, researches revealed that there is a positive association between adaptation and the education level of the household head (Zangre *et al.*, 2024; Harvey *et al.*, 2018).

3.1.4 Household Size of Smallholder Farmers

Table 3.4 shows the distribution of children in the study area. 36% of the household heads have one to five children, 57% have six to ten children while 7% have eleven to fifteen children. Household size is also an important factor affecting climate change adaptation because number of children determines the choice of adaptation strategy. Studies have shown that larger family size had enabled farmers to take up labour intensive adaptation measures (Lamichhane *et. al.*, 2022; Danso-Abbeam *et. al.*, 2021). In other words larger households are more willing to choose adaptations options such as soil conservation techniques and chemical treatments that are labour intensive. This means that farmers with fewer children have to either pay extra money to hire labour or forego such adaptation option.

Table 3.4: Household Size of Respondents

Family size	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	72	36
6-10	114	57
11-15	14	7
Total	200	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

3.2: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

3.2.1: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Dagona ward

Result of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies being adopted in Dagona ward is presented in figure 3.1. Analysis shows that 86% of the farmers in the study area diversify their crops, 78% plant their crops very early, 60% grow resistant varieties, 30% use soil and water conservation practices, 54% have developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall, 0% practice agro-forestry, 20% sell their livestock to adapt to climate change, while 12% do not use any adaptation strategy.

Figure 3.1: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Dagona ward

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

3.2.2: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Gwiyo ward

Result of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies being adopted in Gwiyo kura ward is presented in figure 3.2. Analysis shows that 68% of the farmers in the study area diversify their crops, 60% plant their crops very early, 52% grow resistant varieties, 20% use soil and water conservation practices, 46% have developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall, 0% practice agro-forestry, 16% sell their livestock to adapt to climate change, while 14% do not use any adaptation strategy.

Figure 3.2: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Gwiyo ward

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

3.2.3: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Sugum-Tagali ward

Result of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies being adopted in Sugum-Tagali ward is presented in figure 3.3. Analysis shows that 90% of the farmers in the study area diversify their crops, 80% plant their crops very early, 62% grow resistant varieties, 34% use soil and water conservation practices, 52% have

developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall, 0% practice agro-forestry, 20% sell their livestock to adapt to climate change, while 10% do not use any adaptation strategy.

Figure 3.3: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies being adopted in SugumTagali ward

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

3.2.4: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Usur-Dawayo ward

Result of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies being adopted in Usur-Dawayo ward is presented in figure 3.4. Analysis shows that 94% of the farmers in the study area diversify their crops, 86% plant their crops very early, 64% grow resistant varieties, 40% use soil and water conservation practices, 60% have developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall, 0% practice agro-forestry, 30% sell their livestock to adapt to climate change, while 0% do not use any adaptation strategy.

Figure 3.4: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Usur-Dawayo ward

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

3.2.5: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Bade LGA

Climate change adaptation strategies being used in Bade LGA is presented in figure 3.5. Data analysis show that 84.5% of the farmers in the study area diversify their crops, 76% plant their crops very early, 59.5% grow resistant varieties, 31% use soil and water conservation practices, 53% have developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall, 0% use agro-forestry, 21.5% sell their livestock to adapt to climate change, while 9% do not use any adaptation method.

Result of FGD on climate change adaptation strategies uncover that Majority of the participants in the study area diversify their crops, practice early planting and grow resistant varieties of crops. About half of the population of the farmers use soil and water conservation practices, and have developed irrigation infrastructure to supplement rainfall. Only few of the participants sell their livestock to adapt to climate change because not every farmer own livestock, while very negligible percentage confessed that they do not use any adaptation method. Finally no farmer practices agro-forestry at all.

The AEOs confided that all the farmers in the study area practice crop diversification, early planting, plant drought resistance varieties and have developed irrigation infrastructure. The AEOs also reported that 50% of the farmers practices soil and water management practices and sell their livestock, while none adopted agro-forestry.

Fig 3.5: Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Bade LGA

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

Although these results vary with the results obtained by Bryan *et al.* (2013) in terms of planting trees (agro-forestry) and sell of livestock, they are similar in the area of crop diversification, early planting, growing drought resistant varieties, soil and water conservation practices, and development of irrigation infrastructure. Agro-forestry is not used at all by farmers in the study area; instead they even cut the few trees that grew there naturally because they serve as habitats for birds that attack their crops when they start to seed every year. This fact was explained by some of the farmers during the FGD session. More so, this result does not compare well with that of Alemayehu and Bewket (2017) (where 85% sell livestock, 76% change consumption pattern, 89% Change crop planting dates, 10% practice irrigation). Even though both researches found selling livestock and changing planting dates as adaptation strategies, the percentages vary significantly. Another difference is that while 53% develop irrigation infrastructure in the study area, only 10% do that in Alemayehu and Bewket's research.

Again, this result compare well to that of Fadina and Barjolle (2018) in the area of soil and water conservation, use of improved crop varieties and crop diversification, but vary in terms of planting of trees/perennial plantation and diversification of income generating activities. Likewise, Elum, Modise and

Marr (2017) also found planting drought-tolerant varieties as a common adaptation strategy among the farmers of Gauteng, Limpopo and Mpumalanga in South Africa.

3.3 Effectiveness of the Adaptation Strategies

Farmers in Bade Local Government Area have adopted an array of adaptation strategies such as crop diversification, early planting, growing drought resistant varieties, soil and water conservation practices, development of irrigation infrastructure, and selling of livestock. Although the farmers have confirmed these strategies to be effective during the Focus Group Discussion, yet they were of the opinion that some strategies like crop diversification and early planting are more effective than the others because they are cheaper to adopt. On the other hand however, some of the strategies are expensive to adopt. For example irrigation facilities are costly nowadays and most farmers cannot afford them. Meanwhile, the recent hike in fuel price due the removal of subsidy has exacerbated the situation. Improved seed varieties are now scarce and therefore difficult to access. Soil and water management practices are labour intensive and so farmers with small household size require extra money to pay labourers. Finally, only farmers that own livestock can sell their stock to adopt the capital intensive strategies.

3.4 Inferential Statistical Analysis

A chi-square analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 to explore the relationships between socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers and adaptation strategies. Results of cross tabulations between age of farmers and adaptation strategies, family size (number of children) and adaptation strategies, as well as education level of farmers and adaptation strategies have been presented in tables 3.5, 3.6, and 3.7.

Table 3.5: Farm Level Adaptation Strategies and Age of Farmers

Adaptation Strategies	Age				Total
	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-75	
Crop Diversification	57	68	37	6	168
Early Planting	45	63	37	6	151
Growing Drought Resistant Varieties	30	53	31	6	120
Soil and Water Conservation Practices	4	32	23	5	64
Devt. of Irrigation Infrastructure	23	46	31	6	106
Selling of Livestock	5	19	18	2	44
No Adaptation	18	0	0	0	18
Total	82	73	39	6	200

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

Results in table 3.5 were subjected to chi-square test at $p \leq 0.05$ and the calculated value was found to be 27.63 while the critical value is 25.00. Thus, the relationship is significant since the calculated value is greater than the critical value. This means that age influences the adoption of adaptation strategies. In other words, older farmers are more ready to adopt adaptation strategies than younger ones because of their experience in farming.

Likewise, cross tabulated results of number of children and adaptation strategies (as in table 3.6) were subjected to chi-square test at $p \leq 0.05$ and the calculated value is found to be 24.16 when the critical value is 18.31. The relationship here is also significant since the calculated value is greater than the critical value. This implies that farmers with larger families adopt adaptation strategies (particularly labour intensive strategies) more than those with fewer children.

Table 3.6: Farm Level Adaptation Strategies and Family Size

Adaptation Strategies	Number of Children			Total
	1-5	6-10	11-15	
Crop Diversification	50	104	14	168
Early Planting	35	102	14	151
Growing Drought Resistant Varieties	22	87	11	120
Soil and Water Conservation Practices	2	50	12	64
Devt. of Irrigation Infrastructure	18	76	12	106
Selling of Livestock	6	30	8	44
No Adaptation	18	0	0	18
Total	72	114	14	200

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

In the same vain, results in table 3.7 were subjected to chi-square test at $p \leq 0.05$ and the calculated value was found to be 10.23 while the critical value is 25.00. Therefore, it can be inferred that the relationship is not significant in this case since the calculated value is lower than the critical value. This means that education level of farmers does not influence farmers' adoption of adaptation strategies. This inference is supported by information gathered during the FGD where farmers interviewed confessed that the more educated farmers among them are government employees as such they do not take farming seriously.

Table 3.7: Farm Level Adaptation Strategies and Level of Education

Adaptation Strategies	Level of Education					Total
	Pry Cert.	SSCE	ND/NCE	HND/Degree	Master	
Crop Diversification	28	61	66	12	1	168
Early Planting	26	57	55	11	2	151
Growing Drought Resistant Varieties	25	38	44	11	2	120
Soil and Water Conservation Practices	19	24	16	4	1	64
Devt. of Irrigation Infrastructure	20	42	34	8	2	106
Selling of Livestock	11	22	10	1	0	44
No Adaptation	0	3	13	1	1	18
Total	28	68	85	16	3	200

Source: Fieldwork, 2026.

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the objectives of this work, it is concluded that the impacts of climate change are evident in Bade Local Government Area and smallholder farmers are vulnerable to them. Consequently, they have adopted an array of adaptation strategies in order to cushion its effects which were confirmed to be effective. Prominent among the adaptation strategies are crop diversification, early planting, growing drought resistant varieties of crops, soil and water conservation practices, development of irrigation infrastructure, and selling of livestock.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research a number of recommendations have been put forward:

- 1) It has been observed that agro-forestry; integrating trees and crop cultivation on the same piece of land which is a very good adaptation strategy is not being practiced in the study area. Therefore it is recommended that farmers in the study area be enlightened about the prospects of agro-forestry by relevant stakeholders like the Yobe State Agricultural Development Programme through their Agricultural Extension Services.

- 2) The results of this study show that many farmers diversify their crops to adapt to climate change. Agricultural institutions therefore need to identify those crops being diversified in the study area in order to provide improved varieties that can withstand drought as well as diseases and pests, and mature quickly.

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